

END-EFFECTORS FOR PLY PLACEMENT AND CONSOLIDATION IN LOW COST COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

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SUMMARY: An overview of end-effector design methodology necessary for ply placement and manipulation of dry reinforcement fabric and prepregs for composite manufacture is presented. Needle grippers, adhesive grippers, electrostatic grippers and vacuum grippers are discussed. Vacuum grippers were chosen as the most appropriate method for the pick and place task under consideration. Tests results for maximum suction force and shear force are presented here to demonstrate the suitability of this system.

The integration of these end-effectors into a low-cost, automated composite manufacturing cell is described with emphasis on the development of a demonstration system. This demonstration system is designed to pick, place and consolidate carbon prepreg tapes.

KEYWORDS: Automated manufacture, stringer production, ply lay-up, robotic end-effector, vacuum ports, prepreg tape and fabric.

INTRODUCTION

The current methods for manufacturing composite structures are based mainly on hand techniques. These are very expensive and are prone to variations in the end products. If these tasks are automated, not only the variations are reduced but quality can be maintained. The running costs of such a composite manufacturing cell can be reduced in the long term.

There is very little information in the open literature concerning the design of end-effectors for placement and manipulation of fabrics for composite manufacture. These end-effectors are devices attached to the distal end of the robot arm to perform various tasks of the lay-up process like pick, place and consolidation. The design of such end-effectors presents difficulties in handling the flexible, porous and easily deformable nature of the prepreg tape and

fabric. Added to these difficulties are stringent guidelines to control contaminants like water ingress.

During a typical automated lay-up task, the sub-tasks involved are:

- Cut the composite material to a desired shape or profile.
- Pick the profile and place to a stack or to a position for consolidation.
- Consolidate the profile to the shape of the mold.

These three sub-tasks are best visualised by reference to Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Tasks Involved During A Typical Lay-Up

Based on the author's own extensive literature review, it was found that cutting is now a well established area and need not be investigated. However, the end-effectors performing the remaining two sub-tasks, pick&place and consolidation, need further examination. The end-effectors discussed here are used during these latter two stages of the lay-up process.

The review conducted suggested there is little or no methodology available in the literature to help an engineer in designing end-effectors. An engineer still does not know enough about the parameters governing the pick, place and consolidation stages of the lay-up task. There are few guidelines as to how one should design an end-effector to suit. The highly flexible, tacky and sometimes porous nature of the materials to be handled causes difficulty in the design of suitable end effectors^[2,5-7].

An overview of end-effector designs published in the literature suggested four general types available for pick, place and consolidation. Monkman [8] referred to these as impactive grippers, ingressive grippers, contigutive grippers and astrictive grippers. Impactive grippers are usually in the form of claws and are unsuitable for handling composite fabrics or tapes. Ingressive grippers are needle and card wire types (Schulz [9]). They can be used to remove the backing sheet off prepreg fabrics, but where fibre damage is to be avoided, use of this type should be subject to caution.

Contigutive grippers are adhesive grippers. Examples include Peltier elements (Schulz [9]) and using a rubber pad to pick up prepregs using the prepreg tack (Peck [2]). The main advantage here is that no damage is inflicted to the fibres. However, contaminants and repeated use can reduce performance and reliability.

Astrictive grippers are those grippers that provide a binding force to make prehension possible without initial contact. Examples include electrostatic devices (Monkman [8]), vacuum ports (Ruth and Mulgaonkar [1]) and pads (Peck [2]). Of the four types of grippers, this type is the most versatile and reliable. For vacuum grippers, air-flow requirements can be determined to prevent fibre damage and allow variable suction force. Ply detachment is easily obtainable via reverse air-flow. Electrostatic gripping devices (EGDs) have been shown to be effective, but pose occupational health and safety issues. This is due to the high running voltages used. Kolluru et al. [10] quoted a running voltage of 4000V against a resistance of 100M Ω which was dangerous not only to humans but to nearby electrical components as well.

Based on the information presented, vacuum end-effectors were further investigated. This type appears to be the safest and most viable option to handle prepregs and fabrics made from glass and carbon fibres. The designs of these end-effectors and their operation parameters were investigated and are presented here.

VACUUM ASSISTED END-EFFECTORS DESIGNS

The end-effectors developed and tested are all vacuum end-effectors. The end-effectors presented here played an important role in providing the groundwork for the design of larger end-effectors required in the pick & place system. This is discussed later. Five different designs are presented here. End-effectors used for consolidation are not presented in this paper.

Caps 1 to 4 are vacuum port designs with various different suction surface properties. These suction ports present the first generation of suction fingers intended to be incorporated into the automated lay-up cell. The final design, the honeycomb box, is a rectangular box whose suction surface is defined by a series of hexagonal cells. This honeycomb box was is an alternative to the Cap 4 design whereby the suction surface is a reinforced steel fly-screen.. Following are the details of these end-effectors.

Cap 1 - 20mm ID, 1mm slits

The design of this end-effector is based on the use of the smallest practical drill diameter available. The circular design was selected to minimise the effect of fibre orientation during pick ups. A photograph is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Cap 1 - 1mm slits

Cap 2 - 20mm ID, 152 ordered 1mm diameter holes

This cap is similar to Cap 1 in size and shape with the exception of having 1mm diameter holes instead of 1mm slits. The holes are drilled in an ordered fashion at various angular increments. The benefits of having holes instead of slits are compared later. A photograph is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Cap 2 - 152 x 1mm diameter holes

Cap 3 - 50mm diameter suction surface of 1mm slits

This end-effector represents perhaps the limit of the 1mm slit designs. Any size larger than this would be too time consuming to manufacture (note the cost). A photograph is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Cap 3 - 50mm diameter suction surface of 1mm slits

Cap 4 - 1mm² reinforced steel fly-screen as suction surface

This end-effector introduces a 1mm² reinforced steel fly-screen as the suction surface. The flanges are angled and have been glued to 0.8mm thick neoprene rubber sheet. The angled rubber flange is required to increase shear force and reduces air leakage during pick ups.

A sketch of Cap 4 is given in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Cap 4

Honeycomb box

The idea behind the honeycomb construction comes from the Cap 4 design whereby the fly-screen was used as the reinforcement structure. Here, glass phenolic hexagon honeycomb is used to flatten out the suction surface, while at the same time provided a stiff structure strong enough to withstand high vacuum pressure. Losses due to air flow through the honeycomb structure is kept at minimum by careful design. A sketch is given in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Honeycomb Box

END-EFFECTOR PERFORMANCE

The performance of end-effectors earlier can be described in two ways. The first is the pick-up performance which was based on the maximum pick-up force applied to the fabric. This force is denoted F_m and is based on three or more successful pick-ups performed consecutively. The pick-up action is best summarised on Fig. 7.

The second is the shear force performance based on maximum shear force the end-effector can exert onto the fabric or tape before slippage starts. This is denoted by F_s . It is important since slippage is detrimental to the consolidation process. Slippage causes undesirable fibre orientation and ply positioning during consolidation. The test set-up for determining F_s is given on Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: Pick-up Force Set Up

Fig. 8: Shear Test Set Up

Pick-Up Performance

Test results are shown in Table 1 for a number of composite reinforcement materials. Each value on Table 1 is an average of three or more consecutive tests. The results for prepreg tape and fabric are very promising. Cap1 with a suction diameter of 20mm was able to apply a pick-up force of 4.5N to a piece of prepreg tape with no marking. If four of these caps were used at four corners of a large rectangular prepreg tape, then a total force of 18N would be available for pick up over an area of 8.3m²! It is safe to conclude the end-effectors designed can exert sufficient force to overcome the fabric weights reliably. Note that all results presented here are based on a vacuum source whose maximum vacuum can only reach -20 kPag.

Contrary to expectation, the performance of the honeycomb box design, was very poor. Too much leakage was observed, making this end-effector unsuitable. This is a concern for flat bed end-effectors. It is hoped that future flat bed designs, like the ones to be built for the demonstration cell, will overcome the leakage.

To sum up, the results obtained in this section is a vital component in developing the demonstration cell. The extremes between reliable pickup to fibre damage is established. However, more data is required if one is to optimise the end-effector designs and their performances.

Shear Force Performance

The shear force performance of end-effectors is the second most important parameter during the consolidation stage. Currently there is no information available in the literature relating the suction force of end-effectors to the shear force they can exert to the composite fabrics before slippage starts. In order to find the maximum force before slippage occurs, the effectors Cap 1 to Cap 4 were tested for how much shear force they can exert on dry glass fabric, dry carbon fabric, prepreg fabric and tape. This is important since for controlled consolidation, slippage of the fabric or tape during placement incurs position errors.

The shear test results described here would be the first step in establishing the load requirements of vacuum assisted end-effectors required to hold a piece of fabric in place. This is particularly important and useful if one wishes to optimise the lay-up sequence.

The test results are shown in Table 2 and each results is an average of three or more consecutive repeats. A quick summary of shear force performance for these caps is given on Table 2 where maximum shear forces for each end-effector is shown. The honeycomb box was not tested here since too much leak was detected during the test and results were unreliable. For T300 prepreg fabric, Table 2 shows an increase in shear force for Cap 1 and 2 when the shear force (F_s) direction is at 45° to the warp or weft direction of the fabric. For the larger end-effector, this effect is less significant. Cap 4 shear force results are almost identical for the 45° and axial directions.

Since Cap 1 and 4 suction heads are of similar design containing holes, the results for T300 prepreg fabric seemed to indicate that shear force is dependent on fibre orientation. Values for axial shear force are lower than the shear force at 45°. This trend is visible on Table 2.

However, the effect of orientation on shear force performance is also related to the design of the end-effectors' suction head. Results for Cap 3 with dry fabrics in Table 2 suggests the opposite trend. Axial shear force with dry fabrics is greater than a 45° shear force for the Cap 3 design.

The magnitudes of shear force measured, as shown in Table 2, suggest that there is no need to design vacuum suction ports larger than Cap 3 or Cap 4 (48mm in diameter). The table also suggests that end-effectors suction heads should be larger than 20mm diameter (the Cap 1 and Cap 2 designs). Therefore for point to point fabric manipulation, it is now possible to exert enough shear force to deform dry and prepreg fabrics. The normal force results discussed previously back this point further in that not only a piece of fabric can be sheared, but can be held and pick up reliably. Note that these shear forces can be easily doubled or tripled by using two or three caps.

Lastly, Cap 3 and 4 shear force results can be compared to the maximum pinch force a human thumb and index finger can apply comfortably. Table 2 shows that Caps 3 and 4 can exert greater shear force on a prepreg tape or fabric than a human thumb and index finger. With dry fabrics, only the Cap 4 design can exert shear force that is comparable to a that of a human operator.

END-EFFECTOR NAME:	Honeycomb Box	CAP 1	CAP 2	CAP 3	CAP 4
Material	$F_m(N)$	$F_m(N)$	$F_m(N)$	$F_m(N)$	$F_m(N)$
Uni-directional prepreg tape	4.5 (P_{max} , NM)	4.5 (P_{max} , NM)	2.9 (P_{max} , NM)	5.3 (P_{max} , NM)	3.7 (M) 13.6 (FT)
Uni-directional prepreg tape & backing sheet	-	-	-	5.6 (P_{max})	5.8 (M) 16.8 (FS)
T300 prepreg fabric	Too much leak	2.9 (P_{max} , NM)	2.7 (P_{max} , NM)	4.0 (P_{max} , NM)	14.0 (NM, FS)
T300 prepreg fabric & backing sheet	Too much leak	-	-	4.9 (P_{max})	14.6 (NM, FS)
Satin glass dry fabric	Too much leak	-	-	-	5.7 (P_{max})
Plain weave glass dry fabric	Too much leak	-	-	-	3.4 (P_{max})
Plain weave dry carbon fabric	Too much leak	-	-	1.3 (P_{max})	8.2 (P_{max})

Results are in Newtons (N) with an accuracy of $\pm 0.2N$.

Keys: P_{max} - at maximum pump/vacuum cleaner applied pressure

NM - no marking

M - marking visible

FS - fabric starts to shrink into end-effector's cap

FT - fabric/tape fibres torn

Table 1: Maximum Suction Force Applied For Cap 1 - 4 & Honeycomb box

END-EFFECTOR NAME:	A human thumb & index finger		CAP 1		CAP 2		CAP 3		CAP 4	
	Pull Direction		Pull Direction		Pull Direction		Pull Direction		Pull Direction	
Material	45°	Axial	45°	Axial	45°	Axial	45°	Axial	45°	Axial
Uni-dir. prepreg tape	-	-	-	2.7	-	4.4	-	21.6	-	16.7 ^a
Uni-dir. prepreg tape & backing sheet	-	-	-	3.7	-	3.7	-	19.6	-	23.5
T300 prepreg fabric	17.3	16.4	8.2	3.7	6.5	2.5	-	21.6	25.5	23.5
T300 prepreg fabric & backing sheet			7.5	4.5	5.9	3.1	-	22.1	24.5	24.5
Satin glass dry fabric	14.9	12.8	0.8	0.7	-	-	2.4	3.7	13.7	9.8
Plain weave glass dry fabric	14.7	15.7	-	-	-	-	1.8	1.8	11.8	9.0
Plain weave dry carbon fabric	12.1	12.5	-	-	-	-	2.4	4.6	13.7	9.8

All results are at maximum pump operation and are in Newtons (N) with accuracy of $\pm 0.2N$

Results for the human thumb & index finger refer to pinch test results performed at RMIT.

Note: ^a - prepreg tape starts to shrink into end-effector head

Table 2: Maximum Shear Force(F_s) Acquired For Cap 1 to 4 - 45° & 90° Pull

Other Design Parameters

One of the most important research findings established was the successful use of a single normal force to consolidate of composite fabrics onto double curvature molds. (Do[11]). This led to the development and usage of the air jet, developed by Ma[3], as a compactor tool. Tests performed at RMIT using laboratory pressurized air to compact carbon prepreg fabric did not cause fibre separation during a successful drape. It was also found that a small shear force of 1.6N, applied tangentially to the mould surface, can significantly reduce the consolidation time.

Other parameters which are considered in the research program, but are not discussed here include: backing sheet removal, fabric or tape porosity, stiffness/bending, 3D shape prediction model, system integration and porosity effects due to the interaction between end-effectors and the fabric being picked up.

System integration for automated composite manufacture

To successfully develop an automated composite manufacturing cell, system integration of these end-effectors and their tasks are then looked at and investigated. This has been discussed by Peck[2]).

Currently, a lay-up cell is being developed to demonstrate the principles of automation using the end-effectors designs discussed earlier. This system is expected to be in its demonstration phase in July 1999. The design of this system is aimed at reducing the repetitive labour involved in the manufacture of simple composite components made from carbon tape or fabric prepreg.

CONCLUSION

The use of vacuum assisted end-effector for pick-up of reinforcement fabrics was successful. End-effectors were able to apply sufficient pick-up force to hold various composite materials such as dry glass fabrics and dry or prepreg carbon fabrics and tapes. Pick-up forces can reach 17N in some cases. Large pieces of fabrics/tapes can be held if multiple(4) suction caps are used. Shear forces measured were comparable to those which could be applied by a human operator using a thumb and index finger to pinch various fabrics. Shear forces of 25N were measured for a 48mm diameter suction end effector. Therefore, the slippage which occurs during consolidation can be controlled.

Enough information has been gathered to develop suitable end-effectors for an automated layup cell.

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